

NOSTRUM

Optimizing Floating Offshore Wind Turbines For Use In The Mediterranean Sea

OPTIMISED AIRFOIL DESIGN USING
MULTI-FIDELITY ANALYSES (FROM
ENGINEERING METHODS TO HIGH-
FIDELITY CFD)

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1. Introduction and Scope

Offshore wind energy plays a key role in the transition to sustainable energy systems. Offshore wind turbines (OSWTs) are complex systems influenced by aerodynamic, structural, acoustic, control, manufacturing, logistical, and techno-economic considerations (1). Floating offshore wind turbines, in particular, offer significant advantages by capturing stronger and more consistent wind resources compared to onshore installations. Most existing offshore wind farms are located in the North Sea, where airfoils have been optimized for high wind speeds and relatively uniform atmospheric conditions (2) (3) (4). However, adapting these designs to new regions, such as the Mediterranean Sea—which is expected to play a critical role in the expansion of the wind energy sector—remains an open challenge (5). In such environments, lower average wind speeds and distinct atmospheric turbulence characteristics require optimizing airfoil geometries to maintain high aerodynamic performance under variable operating conditions (6).

The aerodynamic efficiency of a wind turbine blade is strongly dependent on the shape of its airfoil sections. The evolution of specialized airfoil families for horizontal-axis wind turbines (HAWTs), such as the S8XX, FX, and NREL-S series, has demonstrated the importance of tailoring airfoil designs to the operating environment (7) (8). However, most of these have been developed for northern European wind conditions. To ensure optimal performance in the Mediterranean context, new designs are required. Aeroelastic models, which couple aerodynamic loading with structural dynamics and wind input, are essential for accurately predicting wind turbine performance. Among aerodynamic modeling methods, Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT) is still widely used during early-stage design, but its simplifying assumptions limit its accuracy in complex flow regimes (9) (10). High-fidelity methods such as Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), particularly RANS and URANS solvers, offer better predictive capability at the cost of significantly increased computational time. For this reason, multi-fidelity optimization frameworks have become an effective solution for balancing accuracy and efficiency in wind turbine design (11) (12). This activity focuses on the design and optimization of a new family of airfoils derived from the DTU FFA-W3 series, currently used in the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine (13). The goal is to define airfoil geometries that maximize aerodynamic performance—specifically the lift-to-drag ratio—across a range of Reynolds numbers, thickness distributions, and angles of attack, as defined in WP2. Secondary objectives include increasing torque generation at low cut-in wind speeds and reducing noise emissions. Part of the work presented is also reported within the framework of the two Master's projects (14)(15), which are acknowledged for the contribution and collaboration to the development and application efforts in the initial part of the activity.

The optimization process is organized in three main phases: i) develop a multi-fidelity design pipeline that combines rapid simulations and high-fidelity solvers. Initially, the aerodynamic performance of candidate airfoils is evaluated using XFOIL, a fast, panel-based solver that couples inviscid and boundary-layer models. The use of XFOIL enables quick initial assessments and supports the construction of a surrogate model through adaptive sampling. Parallel to this, high-fidelity CFD simulations using RANS and URANS solvers in *Ansys Fluent* are conducted on selected candidates, incorporating laminar-to-turbulent transition modeling (Langtry–Menter γ -R θ SST) to improve drag prediction and separation behavior; ii) training of a stochastic Radial Basis Function (RBF) surrogate model, which is continuously refined to improve local accuracy via adaptive sampling (16) (17) using

the two different fidelity levels aerodynamic results; iii) integration of the surrogate model into a Genetic Algorithm (GA) to perform global optimization of the airfoil shape.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology adopted for the airfoil optimization, including the parameterization strategy, aerodynamic modeling techniques, and the surrogate-based optimization framework. Section 3 describes the implementation and results of the optimization for selected FFA-W3 profiles. Section 4 discusses the performance of the optimized airfoils in comparison to the reference geometries, and Section 5 outlines the main conclusions and directions for future developments.

2. Methods

The optimization and simulation framework developed in this work is applied to the aerodynamic optimization of wind turbine blade sections, with the aim of maximizing aerodynamic efficiency under low-wind conditions typical of the Mediterranean Sea.

The first step is the selection of the objective function that is to improve the lift-to-drag performance of selected sections of the reference turbine, ultimately enabling higher energy extraction at lower cut-in speeds and supporting the cost-effectiveness of next-generation floating offshore systems. The objective function is given in the equation below:

$$OF = E = \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} E(\alpha) d\alpha$$

The function $E(\alpha)$ is constructed by an interpolation of the C_L/C_D values calculated for a range of given degrees.

The second step is the definition of the airfoil blade parametrization. Due to the geometric complexity of airfoil shapes, which cannot be captured by simple analytic expressions, a curve-based parametric model is adopted. In this work, the airfoil geometry is represented using cubic B-spline interpolation, with a reduced set of control points defined along the mean camber line. This approach allows for the generation of new, smooth, and manufacturable geometries while keeping the number of optimization variables low. Initially, the airfoil contour is discretized, and a curvilinear abscissa is introduced to define the arc-length parameter, which is normalized over the total length of the profile. A set of 12 control points is then placed along the airfoil surface (six per side), allowing for a compact yet flexible description of the shape. These control points are not used directly to define the suction and pressure surfaces; instead, their midpoints—lying along the mean camber line—are computed and used as the actual design variables. Each pair of opposing points (one on the suction side and one on the pressure side) is assumed to be rigidly connected by a straight segment. The central point on this segment defines a point on the mean camber line.

This strategy reduces the number of free parameters from 24 (12 x-y coordinates for the full surface) to only 12 (6 x-y coordinates of the meanline), significantly decreasing the dimensionality of the optimization space.

Figure 1: Left: Comparison between the original airfoil geometry (red), the cubic B-spline reconstruction (black), and the control points (blue) used for interpolation. Right: Geometric reconstruction using the mean camber line approach. The orange curves represent the reconstructed airfoil surfaces derived from rigid segments around the meanline (red), with control points symmetrically placed on pressure and suction sides.

The third step involves defining the aerodynamic analysis tool. In this study, two parallel approaches are applied to evaluate the aerodynamic performance of each airfoil configuration: a low-fidelity panel method, based on XFOIL, and a high-fidelity CFD approach, based on 2D RANS simulations. While both frameworks aim to identify geometries that maximize aerodynamic efficiency within the operational conditions typical of the Mediterranean Sea, they follow different philosophies in terms of modeling fidelity, computational cost, and integration within the optimization process.

The first approach, developed with the goal of speed and wide design space exploration, is based on XFOIL, a well-established panel code that couples a linear-vorticity potential flow solver with an integral boundary layer model (18). This method assumes inviscid, incompressible flow around the airfoil surface and accounts for viscous phenomena such as laminar separation, transition, and turbulent boundary layer growth by solving simplified one-dimensional boundary layer equations. The aerodynamic model discretizes the airfoil surface into panels, solving for the circulation and surface velocities using the vortex-source method. The boundary layer equations, including compressible momentum and kinetic energy formulations, are then iteratively coupled with the potential flow solution until convergence is achieved. In this framework, a wide Design of Experiments (DOE) of airfoil geometries—parameterized via B-splines and defined by 12 design variables (6 x- and y-coordinates along the camber line)—is evaluated using XFOIL at Reynolds numbers representative of offshore operating conditions. For each airfoil, simulations are run across a range of angles of attack from 2° to 8° , and the aerodynamic efficiency, defined as the integral of C_L/C_D , is computed and used as the objective function. This model enables rapid evaluation of up to 10^4 airfoil geometries, forming the aerodynamic dataset for training a surrogate model and guiding the genetic optimization routine.

In contrast, the second approach is based on high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations and is designed to provide a more physically detailed characterization of the aerodynamic behavior, particularly under conditions where flow separation, pressure gradients, or transition phenomena significantly influence performance. The CFD framework is implemented in *ANSYS Fluent* and uses a RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes) solver with the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model enhanced by the Langtry–Menter $\gamma - R_\theta$ transition model. This four-equation approach enables accurate tracking of the laminar-turbulent transition onset based on local boundary layer properties and empirical correlations, a crucial feature for evaluating thick airfoils operating near stall or in low-Reynolds conditions.

To ensure grid independence and consistent near-wall resolution, a fully automated meshing routine was developed. The airfoil coordinates, are used as input to a MATLAB script that generates a journal file for ICEM CFD, creating a structured C-type mesh with approximately 190,000 quadrilateral cells. The domain extends 30 chord lengths in all directions, and the mesh near the wall is refined to maintain $y^+ \approx 1$ for all geometries and thicknesses, allowing for full resolution of the viscous sublayer and eliminating the need for wall functions. Once the mesh is generated, Fluent simulations are evaluated. Each airfoil is tested at four angles of attack (2° , 4° , 6° , and 8°), and the aerodynamic coefficients are extracted for objective function computation. The simulations are performed under steady-state, incompressible flow conditions, and a dedicated batch-processing environment ensures reproducibility and speed.

To efficiently explore the aerodynamic design space and reduce the computational cost associated with repeated solver calls, a surrogate model, also known as a metamodel, was implemented. This model approximates the objective function — in this case, the aerodynamic efficiency of the airfoil — based on a limited number of evaluations from the high- or low-fidelity aerodynamic solvers (CFD or XFOIL). Specifically, a Stochastic Radial Basis Function (SRBF) approach was employed, which enables accurate function approximation even with sparse training data while also providing uncertainty quantification.

Given a training set $T = \{x_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^M$ where each x_i is a vector of design variables and $y_i = f(x_i)$ is the corresponding objective function evaluation, the surrogate prediction $\hat{f}(x)$ at a new point x is defined by a weighted sum of radial basis kernels:

$$\hat{f}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^M \omega_i \phi(\|x - x_i\|)$$

Where $\phi(\|x - x_i\|)$ is the kernel function, and the weights ω_i are determined by solving the linear system $A\omega = y$, with matrix element $a_{ij} = \phi(\|x_i - x_j\|)$. In this work, a power kernel function is used:

$$\phi(\|x - x_i\|) = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - x_{ik})^2 \right)^{\frac{\epsilon}{2}}$$

Where $\epsilon \in [1,3]$ is a tuning exponent treated as a stochastic variable, uniformly distributed in the chosen interval. Rather than fixing ϵ , a set of predictions is generated across multiple realizations ϵ_i , yielding a stochastic ensemble of surrogate models:

$$S = \{f(x, \epsilon_i): \epsilon_i \sim U[\epsilon_{min}, \epsilon_{max}]\}$$

The final surrogate prediction is obtained as the expected value over this ensemble, approximated using Monte Carlo sampling:

$$\hat{f}(x) \approx \frac{1}{J} \sum_{i=1}^J f(x, \epsilon_i)$$

In addition to the mean prediction, the model also computes an uncertainty band using the 95% confidence interval where the cumulative distribution function (CDF) is approximated over the ensemble of predictions at point x . This uncertainty quantification is critical for guiding adaptive sampling, in which new training points are added where $\tilde{U}_f(x)$ is largest:

$$x_{M+1} = \arg \max \tilde{U}_f(x)$$

This dynamic refinement allows the surrogate to concentrate sampling effort in regions of high model uncertainty, thereby improving both the accuracy of the approximation and the effectiveness of the optimization.

Once the surrogate model has achieved sufficient predictive accuracy, it is used as the fitness function for a Genetic Algorithm (GA), which explores the design space through evolutionary operations such as selection, crossover, and mutation (19) (20). The GA iteratively improves a population of candidate solutions until convergence, guided by the predictions of the SRBF metamodel. This surrogate-assisted GA framework significantly accelerates the optimization process while ensuring high-quality aerodynamic solutions.

3. Case Study

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed multi-fidelity optimization framework, both low- and high-fidelity workflows were applied in parallel to the aerodynamic redesign of the FFA-W3-211 airfoil, which is employed in the tip region of the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine developed by NREL (3). The FFA-W3-211 profile was selected due to its strategic location along the blade span and its availability in the public dataset associated with the IEA 15 MW turbine, enabling both accurate modeling and validation.

Table 1: IEA 15 MW Reference Wind Turbine Specifications, data from (21)

Parameter	IEA 15 MW Reference Wind Turbine
Power rating [MW]	15
Turbine class	IEC Class IB
Rotor diameter [m]	242.2
Specific rating [W/m ²]	325.5
Rotor orientation	Upwind
Number of blades	3
Control	Variable speed, Collective pitch
Cut-in wind speed [m/s]	3
Rated wind speed [m/s]	10.7
Cut-out wind speed [m/s]	25
Airfoil series	FFA-W3
Hub height [m]	150.0
Hub diameter [m]	7.9
Hub Overhang [m]	-12.0
Drive train	Low speed, Direct drive
Design tip speed ratio	9
Minimum rotor speed [rpm]	5
Maximum rotor speed [rpm]	7.56
Maximum tip speed [m/s]	95

In both optimization pathways, the airfoil geometry was parameterized using a B-spline representation of the mean camber line, reducing the design space to 12 independent variables (six x-y control points). New airfoil geometries were generated by rigidly reconstructing the suction and pressure sides from the meanline via symmetric displacements, allowing for smooth and manufacturable shapes throughout the optimization process.

In the first approach, the aerodynamic performance of each candidate geometry was evaluated using XFOIL, which combines a potential flow solver with an integral boundary layer model. The analysis was conducted at a Reynolds number of 1.0×10^7 , using 300 panels and a maximum of 500 iterations to ensure convergence. The lift and drag coefficients were computed across angles of attack ranging from 2° to 8° , and the fitness function was defined as:

$$F(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha=2^\circ}^{8^\circ} \left(\frac{C_L(\alpha)^2}{C_D(\alpha)} \right)$$

A Stochastic Radial Basis Function (SRBF) surrogate model was trained on the simulation results to approximate the objective function across the design space. The model employed adaptive sampling, guided by model uncertainty, to select new training points iteratively. The optimization was carried out using a Genetic Algorithm, with 100 individuals per generation, 10 mating pairs, a crossover probability of 0.8, and an adaptive mutation scheme. The convergence was monitored through the variance of the surrogate model, which stabilized below 5% after approximately 25 iterations.

In parallel, a high-fidelity CFD-based optimization was performed using RANS simulations with the γ -R0 SST transition model in ANSYS Fluent. The same geometric parameterization was used, and each candidate profile was embedded in a C-type structured mesh composed of approximately 191,668 quadrilateral cells, extending 30 chord lengths in all directions.

Figure 2: Overview of the structured C-type mesh adopted for the CFD simulations of the FFA-W3-211 airfoil. The zoomed inset highlights the high grid density around the airfoil surface

Boundary conditions included a 12 m/s freestream velocity, 0 Pa outlet pressure, and no-slip airfoil wall condition, simulating an operating Reynolds number of 1.8×10^6 . The solver used hybrid initialization, progressing through first-order and second-order schemes with convergence criteria set to 1×10^{-11} . Simulations were performed at four angles of attack (2° , 4° , 6° , and 8°), and a total of 76 geometries were evaluated to construct the high-fidelity surrogate.

The SRBF surrogate for the CFD data and the GA optimization followed the same formulation as in the XFOIL case, obtaining a high computational cost (~80 hours).

3.1 Solver Validation

To assess the reliability and accuracy of the aerodynamic prediction models adopted in this work, two separate validation campaigns were conducted for the XFOIL-based low-fidelity model and the ANSYS Fluent-based high-fidelity CFD simulations.

For the XFOIL approach, the validation focused on comparing the lift and drag coefficients obtained through simulation with reference polar data for the FFA-W3-211 airfoil (Figure 3), available from the DTU technical documentation. The simulation setup used a Reynolds number of $Re = 10^7$, with a total of 300 panels and a maximum of 500 iterations per solution. The angle of attack ranged from $\alpha = 0^\circ$ to $\alpha = 20^\circ$ with an increment of $\Delta\alpha = 0.5^\circ$.

Figure 3: Comparison between C_L and C_D coefficients evaluated using XFOIL with the reference data from IEA 15MW at different angle of attack

The XFOIL results showed good agreement with the reference data in the low angle-of-attack regime, particularly between $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 10^\circ$, which is also the optimization interval of interest. In this range, as you can see in Figure 4, the relative error in C_L remained below 5%, while the prediction of C_D was found to be almost the same. This supports the suitability of XFOIL for low-fidelity preliminary design and confirms the relevance of the selected simulation setting.

Figure 4: Trend of the percentage error evaluated for C_L and C_D coefficients at different angle of attacks.

For the CFD model, a two-phase validation was performed. First, the results from ANSYS Fluent and OpenFOAM were compared against experimental data acquired in the L2000 low-speed wind tunnel at KTH (Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm), under a turbulence intensity of 0.15%. The Fluent solver was found to yield more accurate results in terms of flow separation and drag prediction, and was therefore selected for all further simulations.

Figure 5: Simulation Results for OpenFoam Solver and Ansys Fluent.

Secondly, a sensitivity analysis of the turbulence model parameters was conducted by tuning the shear-stress transport (SST) coefficient a_1 , which governs the eddy viscosity in the $k-\omega$ SST model. Three values were tested: $a_1 = 0.26, 0.275, \text{ and } 0.29$, at a Reynolds number of $1.8 \cdot 10^6$, matching the wind tunnel conditions. Figure 6 shows the comparison of the results and, after that, the optimal value was found to be $a_1 = 0.275$, which minimized the error in C_D and improved the agreement of the predicted aerodynamic efficiency $E(\alpha) = C_L/C_D$ with experimental data.

Figure 6: Simulation results for different values of a_1 turbulent model coefficient.

A comparison between simulation and experiment confirmed the robustness of the Fluent setup, providing a validated baseline for high-fidelity evaluations within the surrogate-assisted optimization loop.

4. Results

This section presents the results of the aerodynamic optimization process performed on the FFA-W3-211 airfoil using the two parallel methodologies described previously: a low-fidelity approach based on XFOIL and a high-fidelity approach using CFD simulations with a surrogate-assisted optimization loop. The goal of the optimization was to enhance aerodynamic efficiency, particularly in the lift-to-drag ratio C_L/C_D , within the range of low angles of attack relevant for offshore wind turbine operation under Mediterranean wind conditions. For both approaches, the initial baseline geometry was parameterized through a reduced set of control points on the mean camber line, and GA was employed to explore the design space defined within the bounds of geometrically feasible variations. In each case, the optimized airfoil configuration was determined as the one maximizing the objective function, defined as the integral of aerodynamic efficiency across a specified angle of attack interval. The following subsections present a comparison between the baseline and optimized airfoils, highlighting the performance improvements achieved in terms of aerodynamic coefficients, flow behavior, and efficiency trends. Separate analyses are provided for each approach, followed by a comparative discussion of the outcomes.

4.2 XFOIL based optimization results

The optimized profile resulting from the XFOIL-based surrogate-assisted optimization is referred to as FFA-W3-211-MS. Starting from the reference airfoil geometry, the optimization framework developed in this study led to a significantly modified shape, as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Geometry comparison between the reference airfoil (FFA-W3-211) with the optimized one (FFA-W3-211-MS)

This new configuration emerged from a large Design of Experiments (DOE), efficiently explored thanks to the flexibility of the XFOIL solver and the low computational cost of the surrogate model. The aerodynamic performance of the optimized profile was evaluated through direct XFOIL simulations, and the corresponding lift and drag curves at a Reynolds number of $Re = 1.0 * 10^7$ are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 8: Comparison of aerodynamic coefficients C_L and C_D of reference profile (FFA-W3-211) and optimized one (FFA-W3-211-MS)

Figure 9: Comparison of aerodynamic efficiency of reference profile (FFA-W3-211) and optimize one (FFA-W3-211-MS)

In particular, within the optimization range of angle of attack $[2^\circ, 8^\circ]$, the FFA-W3-211-MS profile displays consistently higher values of lift coefficient C_L and lower values of drag coefficient C_D , resulting in a substantial improvement of the aerodynamic efficiency.

The reliability of the optimization process is further supported by the comparison between the value of the objective function predicted by the surrogate model and the value obtained by directly evaluating the optimized profile using XFOIL simulations (Table 2). This comparison shows a close agreement between the two, meaning that the surrogate model was able to accurately approximate the behavior of the real aerodynamic system throughout the design space. In other words, the surrogate model successfully identified a high-performing airfoil shape without requiring a full set of costly simulations.

Table 2: Comparison of XFOIL fitness and Genetic Algorithm with percentage error

$F(t_{op})$ XFOIL	$F(t_{op})$ Algoritmo Genetico	Errore Percentuale (%)
1105.2	1244.3	12.58

A more detailed interpretation of the improvements can be drawn from the pressure coefficient C_p distributions along the chord for different angles of attack, shown in Figure 10. On the suction side, the optimized airfoil geometry shows more negative C_p values up to 30–40% of the chord, indicating a stronger flow acceleration and thus an increase in lift. On the pressure side, the optimized profile exhibits more positive C_p values, enhancing the overall pressure differential and further contributing to lift generation. These effects are particularly evident in the central chord region, while the trailing edge shows minor losses.

Figure 10: Comparison of the C_p of reference profile (FFA-W3-211) and optimize one (FFA-W3-211-MS)

Starting from the hypothesis that the lower wind speeds typical of Southern Europe allow for an increase in blade length, an additional optimization study was carried out on the FFA-W3-182 airfoil. This test followed exactly the same setup and methodology described in the previous sections. The results of the optimization process led to the generation of a new airfoil, named FFA-W3-182-MS. Compared to the optimization of the thicker FFA-W3-211 profile, the optimized geometry of the FFA-W3-182-MS shows smaller deviations from the original shape, as shown in. This outcome is primarily due to the reduced Design of Experiments (DOE) space, a necessary constraint imposed to ensure that the thinner airfoil profiles remained within the range of configurations that could still be accurately analyzed using XFOIL.

Figure 11: Geometry comparison between the reference airfoil (FFA-W3-182) with the optimized one (FFA-W3-182-MS)

The effectiveness of the optimization process applied to the FFA-W3-182 profile is further confirmed by the comparison between the predicted fitness value from the surrogate model and the actual aerodynamic performance calculated via XFOIL. As reported in Table 3, the optimized profile yields a fitness value of 870.46 from the Genetic Algorithm, while the corresponding XFOIL validation provides a slightly lower value of 835.41, resulting in a percentage error of just 4.19%.

Table 3: Comparison of XFOIL fitness and Genetic Algorithm with percentage error

$F(t_{op})$ XFOIL	$F(t_{op})$ Algoritmo Genetico	Errore Percentuale (%)
835.41	870.46	4.19

Figure 12: Comparison of aerodynamic coefficients C_L and C_D of reference profile (FFA-W3-182) and optimized one (FFA-W3-182-MS)

Figure 13: Comparison of aerodynamic efficiency of reference profile (FFA-W3-182) and optimized one (FFA-W3-182-MS)

As illustrated in Figure 12 and Figure 13, the optimized airfoil demonstrates a modest improvement in aerodynamic performance within the target range of angles of attack, specifically between 2° and 8°. In this interval, the optimized profile exhibits a slight increase in the lift coefficient (C_L) compared to the baseline airfoil, as well as a notable enhancement in aerodynamic efficiency, measured by the lift-to-drag ratio.

Further insight into the aerodynamic performance is provided by the pressure coefficient (C_p) distributions along the chord, as shown in Figure 14. The comparison of C_p curves highlights a trend similar to the one observed for the FFA-W3-211-MS: on the suction side, up to approximately 30%–40% of the chord, the optimized profile shows more negative C_p values, indicating a higher local flow acceleration and thus greater lift generation. On the pressure side, the C_p values are more positive in the central region of the chord, increasing the overall pressure difference across the profile and contributing to an improved lift force.

Figure 14: Comparison of the C_p of reference profile (FFA-W3-182) and optimize one (FFA-W3-182-MS)

These enhancements are especially noticeable at angles of attack of 2° and 4° , while for higher angles, the differences between the optimized and original profiles become less significant. In conclusion, as expected, the FFA-W3-182-MS airfoil, despite its smaller geometric deviation from the original design, achieves a slight improvement in aerodynamic performance.

4.3 CFD based optimization results

The CFD-based optimization process applied to the FFA-W3-211 airfoil led to the identification of a new optimized geometry, referred to as FFA-W3-221, obtained through the surrogate model coupled with a genetic algorithm. After 100 iterations and only 76 high-fidelity CFD evaluations, the surrogate model was able to guide the optimization toward an airfoil delivering an 8.08% increase in the objective function compared to the baseline. The optimized geometry is presented in Figure 15, while a direct comparison between the two airfoils is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 15: Optimal airfoil obtained by the genetic algorithm

Figure 16: Comparison between the baseline airfoil FFA-W3-211 and the optimized FFA-W3-221. From top left to bottom right: lift coefficient vs angle of attack, drag coefficient vs angle of attack, lift coefficient vs drag coefficient, and aerodynamic efficiency curve $E(\alpha)$.

To assess the reliability of the surrogate model, the optimized profile was re-evaluated using full CFD simulations. The results of this validation, reported in Table 4, confirm a strong agreement between the surrogate-based prediction and the CFD-calculated performance, with only 1.7% error on the objective function value. Additionally, it was verified that the same optimal shape could be recovered even with only 65 training samples, albeit with a slightly higher prediction error of 2.4%.

Table 4: Comparison of Max Objective function results Surrogate plus Genetic Algorithm with CFD

	Surrogate + Genetic A.	CFD	Error
max(OF)	807.3	793.6	1.7%
OF gain	8.08 %	6.25 %	1.7%

From an aerodynamic perspective, the optimized airfoil achieves higher performance within the target angle of attack range (2° – 8°), especially between 4° and 8° , which was prioritized during the adaptive sampling process. As illustrated in Figure 16, the gain in aerodynamic efficiency is achieved by a combination of reduced drag and increased lift, particularly at moderate angles of attack. Notably, the stall point occurs earlier due to the shifted lift curve, indicating a design tailored to maximize performance before the onset of stall. Geometric modifications are more pronounced on the suction side, particularly around 20% of the chord length, where the maximum thickness is shifted rearward. This adjustment helps create a larger low-velocity zone, increasing suction and hence lift, as visualized in the velocity contour plot (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Optimal (top) and FFA-w3-211 (bottom) Contour Plot for velocity at 8° Angle of Attack

The pressure coefficient distributions, shown in Figure 18, further highlight the improved aerodynamic behavior of the optimized profile across different angles of attack (6° , 8° , and 10°). In all cases, the optimized airfoil exhibits a greater pressure difference between the upper and lower surfaces, correlating with the observed lift increase.

Figure 18: Pressure Coefficient for the baseline and the optimal airfoil at $\alpha = 6^{\circ}$, $\alpha = 8^{\circ}$, and $\alpha = 10^{\circ}$.

Finally, the Skin Friction Coefficient (C_f), presented in Figure 19 and Figure 20, confirms that the Langtry-Menter transition model correctly captures the laminar-turbulent transition on both airfoils. Compared to the baseline, the optimized geometry shows a more favorable distribution of C_f on the suction side, helping delay separation and improving the overall aerodynamic efficiency.

Figure 19: Skin Friction Coefficient C_f for FFA-W3-211 at $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $\alpha = 4^\circ$.

Figure 20: Skin Friction Coefficient C_f for the optimize airfoil at $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $\alpha = 4^\circ$.

5. Conclusions

This work presented the development and application of a multi-fidelity aerodynamic optimization framework tailored to floating offshore wind turbines operating under the low-wind conditions typical of the Mediterranean Sea. The methodology combined rapid low-fidelity simulations using XFOIL with high-fidelity CFD analyses in ANSYS Fluent, integrated within a surrogate-assisted genetic algorithm optimization loop. Two parallel optimization paths were executed on airfoil sections from the FFA-W3 series—specifically FFA-W3-211 and FFA-W3-182—highlighting the potential and trade-offs of each approach.

The XFOIL-based optimization, enabled by the fast computation and wide design space exploration, led to the definition of optimized profiles (FFA-W3-211-MS and FFA-W3-182-MS) with improved lift-to-drag ratios in the operational angle of attack range (2° – 8°). The aerodynamic gains were more evident for the thicker FFA-W3-211 profile, where the optimization process introduced more pronounced geometric modifications, whereas the thinner FFA-W3-182 airfoil showed a more constrained evolution due to shape limitations imposed by XFOIL's numerical stability. In both cases, the optimized airfoils exhibited more favorable pressure coefficient distributions and confirmed the effectiveness of the surrogate model, which reached convergence with limited training points and maintained prediction errors below 5%.

In parallel, a CFD-based optimization was conducted on the FFA-W3-211 airfoil. Using a high-resolution RANS framework enhanced by the Langtry–Menter transition model and structured C-type meshing, the optimization resulted in a new geometry (FFA-W3-221) with an aerodynamic efficiency improvement of over 8% compared to the baseline. The surrogate model accurately predicted the performance with only 1.7% error when validated against full CFD simulations,

confirming the robustness of the optimization pipeline even under high-fidelity constraints. Detailed flow analyses revealed significant modifications in the suction side geometry, beneficial pressure coefficient profiles, and delayed flow separation due to improved transition behavior.

Overall, this study demonstrated the viability of surrogate-based optimization using both low- and high-fidelity aerodynamic solvers. The flexibility and speed of the XFOIL-based approach are particularly beneficial during early-stage design and large design space exploration, while CFD-based optimization ensures higher accuracy and physical realism, especially for thick profiles or near-stall conditions. The hybrid use of both methods, guided by adaptive sampling and stochastic surrogate modeling, represents a powerful design strategy for the next generation of floating wind turbines optimized for Mediterranean deployment.

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